

Carbon dots : Chemistry, properties and applications[†]

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Abstract : Carbon dots (C-dots) are a new class of carbon nanomaterials having size of less than 10 nm. C-dots have been emerged as a star in field of fundamental and technical importance due to its alluring properties. Here in this paper, we have described synthetic routes for fabrication of C-dots. There are several methods for the synthesis of carbon dots, but in this report we have mainly emphasized on hydrothermal, solvothermal and microwave methods. Since these methods are very simple, fast, cost-effective and also do not require very high temperature hence energy efficient and environment friendly. The toxicity concerns can also be overcome with use of green precursors. These methods have also proved very efficient in upgradation of waste material and up cycling of negatively valued product into valuable product. Properties of C-dots such as structure, optical properties, chemiluminescence, electrochemiluminescence, *in vitro* and *in vivo* toxicity have been briefly discussed. Further, applications of C-dots in biomedical field and environment concern have also been discussed.

Keywords : Carbon dots, hydrothermal, solvothermal, microwave, chemistry, photoluminescence.

Introduction

Carbon dot (C-dots) is a comprehensive term for several nanosized carbon materials and also known as carbon quantum dots. Basically, all nanosized materials that consist of mainly carbon skeleton can be called C-dots. C-dots always possess at least one dimension smaller than 10 nm in size and fluorescence as its characteristic properties. Carbon quantum dots or carbon dots have become a colossal designation in the field of material science, since its discovery in 2004 during separation of multiwalled carbon nanotubes under electrical influence¹. C-dots have emerged as new advancement in medicine and theranostics due to their exceptional biocompatibility², typical optical properties³, nontoxic precursors as carbon sources, high aqueous solubility, and easy surface passivation, unlike semiconductor quantum dots such as CdTe and CdSe^{4,5} which possess some sort of toxicity. Another luscious property of C-dots is their photoluminescence (PL) in near-infrared region (NIR) which assets the potential use of it for treatment of tumors by employing photo thermal therapy^{6,7}.

There has been remarkable progress in synthetic protocols for fabrication of fluorescent C-dots in the past few years. Widely used among them is microwave irradiated synthesis⁷, laser ablation of graphite⁸, thermal cracking of carbonaceous materials⁹, electro oxidation of graphite¹⁰, and oxidation of soot. Moreover, there are very few reports on synthesis of C-dots using natural plant materials and green waste materials as carbon source. Recently, C-dot has been synthesized using orange juice and commercially available food caramels like jaggery, bread, sugar, etc. as they contain carbohydrate. C-dots derived from natural materials become exceptionally biocompatible as well as cost effective for mass production. C-dots are used as versatile drug delivery carrier for chemotherapeutic payloads due to its exceptional biocompatibility¹¹⁻¹³. Due to over dosage of antibiotics microbial resistance decreases hence C-dots can be used for controlled drug release. Carbon dots possess a number of transcendent properties such as exceptional photostability, small size, biocompatibility, excellent solubility highly tunable photoluminescence (PL) property, ease to be functionalized

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with biomolecules and chemical inertness hence it has emerged as superior and universal organic fluorophores.

Chemistry of quantum dots

Quantum dots (QDs) could be considered as a new kind of fluorophore which are based on inorganic atoms and stabilized by an organic ligand layer. Instead of using organic dyes, QDs have vast applications in the area of medicine, biology, technology and in analytical processes due to their unique properties such as (a) broad absorption spectra, (b) very narrow emission spectra, (c) long fluorescence lifetime and (d) high photostability. QDs are synthesized by atoms of group II (alkyl metals, metal oxides or organic salts) and group VI (Se, S and Te). The QDs should be water soluble in order to use it in bioapplication and analytical chemistry¹⁴.

It is well known fact that in semiconductor materials, the electric current is carried by electrons and holes. The photo generated electron-hole pair is known as an exciton, which, upon recombination, gives rise to the fluorescence emission of QDs¹⁵. The presence of surface states or defect states, as a result of synthesis and the nature of the ligand determine fluorescence efficiency¹⁶. In chemical process, the surface atoms are bound to a high band-gap material and eliminate all energy levels inside the gap^{17,18}.

In practical, semiconducting metallic QD applications are restricted in several fields due to their non-cooperative nature in biocompatibility, hemocompatibility, toxicity and also chemistry of interaction with metabolites and living cells. Hence, it is highly desirable to synthesize C-dots (CDs) through environment friendly synthetic route, using green raw materials because it will have negligible toxicity. In recent years, there are so many research found in natural products such as egg shell, banana, orange, spinach, sugarcane, papaya, pomegranate, ginger, rose flower, rice etc. In this review we have discussed synthetic methods of C-dots from various sources by hydrothermal, solvothermal and microwave treatment and also its properties and applications in various fields.

Methods of C-dots preparation

Laser-Ablation methods :

Laser-Ablation method is fast, effective and surface states tunable method. Sun *et al.*¹⁹ fabricated carbon dots

by laser ablation of a carbon target (hot-pressing of graphite powder and cement mixture) in the presence of argon gas and containing water vapour at 900 °C and 75 kPa, using Nd : YAG laser. C-dots obtained with some modification exhibited bright luminescence emission property. But there are some demerits in this process such as need of very drastic condition; high temperature and pressure. Hence this method is not very useful in respect of environmental and energy efficiency.

Electrochemical carbonization :

Electrochemical carbonization is stable and one-step process. Zhou *et al.*²⁰ produced carbon dots by electrochemical action of multi wall carbon nanotubes in acetonitrile solution (degassed) containing 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as the supporting electrolyte. Upon cycling process the potential maintain between -2.0 and 2.0 V at a scan rate of 500 mV/s, the transparent electrolyte solution firstly changed into yellow then yellow solution changed into dark brown solution. The solution show blue luminescence under the UV lamp. Purified the dark brown solution and removed acetonitrile. Finally carbon dots were obtained. This method is very complicated and time consuming.

Hydrothermal and solvothermal method :

Hydrothermal and solvothermal method is a low cost, eco-friendly and nontoxic method. In this method compound is reacted in a hydrothermal bomb at high temperature then resultant C-dots are formed without need of drastic condition. There are many precursor found such as glucose, ginger, sweet pepper, pomegranate, aloe vera, banana juice, honey, orange juice, milk, chitosan for the fabrication of carbon dots by hydrothermal or solvothermal method²¹⁻⁴⁵. In a typical hydrothermal method to synthesize carbon dots from ginger²¹ is shown in Fig. 1. Other types of hydrothermal and solvothermal process for the synthesis of C-dots is shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of carbon dots from ginger by hydrothermal method.

Table 1. Synthesis of carbon dots by hydrothermal/solvothermal methods

Reactant	Time (h)	Temp. (°C)	Fluorescent	Quantum yield (%)	Size (nm)	Ref.
Sweet pepper	5	180	Blue	19.3	2–7	22
Punica granatum juice	12	170	Blue	7.6	2–5	23
Trapa bispinosa peel	2	90	Green	–	5–10	24
Banana (Musa acuminata) juice, ethanol (oven)	4	150	Green	8.95	1.5–4.5	25
Bagasse's carbonaceous blocks, sodium hydroxide	8	200	Blue	4.7	2.94–5.18	26
Citric acid, Tris(hydroxymethyl)-methylaminomethane	6	250	Blue	54.2	1.7–3.9	27
Coriander leaves	4	240	Green	6.48	1.5–2.98	28
Potatoes	2	180	Blue	15	4–8	29
Soot	15	200	Green	4.96	3	30
Peels of fresh cucumber/pineapple	2	150	Blue	–	50	31
Honey, H ₂ O ₂	2	100	Blue	19.8	–	32
Orange juice	2.5	120	Green	26	1.5–4.5	33
Bovine serum albumin, ethanol	12	180	Blue	7	5–8	34
Gelatin	3	200	Blue	31.6	1.7	35
Orange waste peels, sodium hypochlorite solution, water	12	180	Green	–	2–7	36
Lactose, Tris	24	100	Blue	12.5	1–2	37
Milk	2	180	Blue	12	2–4	38
1,2,4-Triaminobenzene formamide	12	120	Yellow	–	12–16	39
Sodium alginate, tryptophan	6	220	Blue	47.9	13.3	40
Glycerol, OA-POSS	12	230	Blue	24	2–4	41
Chitosan, ethanol	5	150	Blue	–	1–4	42
Ammonium citrate, mannose	2	180	Blue	9.8	2–4.3	43
Neem gum, sodium hydroxide and absolute ethanol	3	30	Blue	–	5–10	44
Pomelo peel	3	200	Blue	6.9	2–4	45

Microwave method :

Microwave irradiation of organic molecules⁴⁶ is a fast and inexpensive method to synthesize C-dots. Microwave offers instant and uniform heating to substrate, hence it is very easy to operate and lessen the reaction time also. Recent study have shown that there are many green precursor such as dextrin, rose, sucrose, glucose, rice citric acid, shrimp egg, raw cashew gum etc.^{47–68} from which C-dots can be easily formed. Recently, Feng *et al.*⁴⁸ have synthesized carbon dots using dried rose flowers as precursor (Fig. 2). The synthesized C-dots have size range from 4–6 nm in diameter which shows blue fluorescence in the presence of UV light and good ultrasensitive detec-

Fig. 2. synthesis of carbon dots from rose petals by microwave method.

tion property of Tetracycline in real samples. Many works based on microwave process has been enlisted in Table 2.

Properties of C-dots**Structure :**

Carbon dots (C-dots) are a new class of carbon nanomaterials having size of less than 10 nm. Sun *et al.*⁶⁹

Table 2. Synthesis of carbon dots by microwave methods

Reactant	Time	Temp./Watt	Fluorescent	Size (nm)	Ref.
PEG1500 and glycerine, serine	10 min	–	Blue	3–4	49
Sucrose, DEG, H ₂ SO ₄	1 min	750 W	Green	5	50
Flour	20 min	180 °C	Blue	1–4	51
Gum arabic, ethanol, sodium hydroxide	5 min	–	Turbid green	7	52
Sucrose, phosphoric acid	11 min	100 W	Green	3–10	53
Rice	30 min	800 W	Blue	1.3–6.4	54
Citric acid, urea	5 min	750 W	Blue	1–5	55
Ethylenediamine, citric acid	3 min	500 W	Blue	–	56
Citric acid, PEI	5 min	850 W	Blue	12	57
Shrimp egg	25 min	180 °C	Blue	2–4.2	58
Citric acid, tetraoctylammoniumbromide	2–3 min	500 W	Blue	4–10	59
Onion	4 h	200 °C	–	–	60
Raw cashew gum	30–40 min	800 W	Blue	9	61
PEG-200	10 min	900 W	Blue	3.4–5.4	62
Sorbitol, sodium hydroxide	2 min	900 W	Blue	5–10	63
Glycerol, APTES	5 min	–	Blue	5	64
Garlic	120 min	200 °C	–	–	65
Glycerol	14 min	750 W	Blue	1–4	66
DMF, acids	2–3 min	700 W	Blue	1–6	67
OPPF6	2 min	450 W	Blue	6	68

reported that carbon dots are quasi-spherical nanoparticles having size less than 10 nm in diameter and some carbon dots are also in hollow-structured^{70,71}. Some studies have also shown amorphous C-dots having geometry like sp² and some are sp³, diamond like structure has also been reported. The shape of C-dots is circular or elliptical, even some have quadrate, triangular and hexagonal structure, which has been confirmed by high resolution TEM, SEM and X-ray diffraction measurements.

Absorbance :

C-dots absorb in short-wavelength region due to π - π^* transition of C=C bonds. They typically show strong optical absorption in the UV region (260–320 nm), with a tail extending into the visible range⁷². Generally, C-dots are relatively more efficient in absorption of long wavelengths. Their absorption characteristics differ from one C-dots to other depending upon surface passivation and functional groups attached on its surface.

Photoluminescence :

The most fascinating feature of C-dots is their tunable photoluminescence (PL) properties arising from quantum confinement effects. The PL quantum yield of bare C-dots is low (typically < 10%) due to the emissive traps on

the surface. In order to enhance the brightness of C-dots, surface passivation is necessary. C-dots with different color have been synthesized, ranging from UV to red, but most of them emit commonly in blue and green region. Undesirable for multi-color imaging, most of the C-dots show broad emission spectra because of the large heterogeneity (in size and chemical composition) resulted from poorly controllable synthesis processes.

Chemiluminescence :

Chemiluminescence (CL) is defined as the production of light through a chemical reaction. CL produces from the excitation of C-dots, after direct oxidation which is formed by electron and hole-injection. With proper reaction condition in redox reaction, CL produce in aqueous phase system and unstable products are generate from intermediate radicals in the CL reaction process. It can be produce emitting species by direct oxidation of objective compound or by indirect enhancing or inhibitory effects of certain luminescence compounds^{73,74}. It can also be produced from the reaction of inorganic molecule but luminescence is weak because quantum yield is low. Therefore, in analytical application the intensity of CL should be enhanced.

Electrochemiluminescence :

Carbon dots show electrochemiluminescence (ECL) properties and also helpful in biosensors, optical devices, metal ions detection^{75,76}. To investigate ECL and PL emissions two different C-dots, surface-state and core-state were worked respectively. Two different carbon dots high (o-Cdots) and low (r-Cdots) oxidation level were synthesized by carbonization-extraction method and acid refluxing method, respectively. Irreversible oxidation peak was observed in o-Cdots. When gold electrode placed by GCE then no peak observed, indicating that in the presence of GCE electrode the electron transfer from o-Cdots and the electrode surface. In r-Cdots, ECL signals were smaller in comparison to the o-Cdots. The ECL mechanism take place near the electrode surface and applied potential beyond the threshold value, foremost the formation of radical from the free shell of the C-dots. These radicals extinguish to produce excited C-dots that emit emission.

In vitro and in vivo toxicity and bioimaging of C-dots :

The carbonaceous C-dots are more biocompatible than other nanomaterials as carbon constitutes the backbone of almost all biomolecules. Hence its excellent and excitation dependent fluorescence can be utilized in bioimaging. Cell viability of >90% and >94% were observed after incubation of HeLa cells MCF-7 cells upto the limit of 7.0 mg/mL with CDs/POSS. This concentration limit is much higher than that of required for bioimaging⁷⁷ N-doped C-dots with brightly yellow fluorescence synthesized by using 1,2,4-triaminobenzene as carbon precursor via solvothermal method was tested by MTT assay for cell toxicity. After incubation of MCF-7 cells for 24 h with the y-CDs (50 µg/mL) over 95% cell survival rate

was observed which confirms very low cytotoxicity of the y-CDs³⁹. C-dots have also been proven to pose negligible cytotoxicity to many other cell lines. It was found in another study that the haemolysis percentage was <1.8% for a C-dot dosage of 60 µg mL⁻¹ (<5% is considered non-haemolytic by ISO guidelines)⁷⁸. Careful *in vivo* toxicity studies of C-dots have been also performed in mice⁷⁹.

Applications of C-dots

The fascinating characteristics of C-dots has been utilized in diverse applications. Fig. 3 depicts the various properties like chemical inertness, soluble, biocompatible and photoluminescence and multipurpose applications of C-dots. Here we described some of the applications with effective results.

Sensing applications :

Recently, Chen's group prepared a new type of C-dots for sensitive and selective detection of quercetin by using N-(β-aminoethyl)-β-aminopropylmethyl-dimethoxysilane and citric acid as starting materials⁸⁰. Phytic acid selectively detected with linear range of 0.68–18.69 µM and a limit of detection of 0.36 µM utilizing the fluorescence off-on probe of C-dots⁸¹. Tetracyclines can be selectively and efficiently detected upto a limit of 3.3×10^{-9} mol/L by C-dots derived by rose flower via microwave irradiation method. Detection of TCs was based on the fact that fluorescent intensity of C-dots is considerably quenched by tetracycline⁴⁸.

Ions of biological importance such as Fe³⁺, Zn²⁺, PO₄³⁻, S₂O₃²⁻ have been sensitively detected employing on the carbon-dots (C-dots) based fluorescent off-on (Fe³⁺, S₂O₃²⁻) and on-off (Zn²⁺, PO₄³⁻) sensors for the detection of metal ions and anions⁸². Besides it metal ions of

Fig. 3. Various properties and multipurpose applications of C-dots.

biological importance and of environmental concern such as Cu^{2+} ⁶⁷, Au(III) ⁷⁶, Hg^{2+} ⁸³, Pb^{2+} (detection limit as low as 15.0 nM)⁸⁴, Ag^+ , Pt(IV) ⁸⁵ can also be detected.

Cellular imaging :

Due to excellent fluorescence, low toxicity and biocompatibility, C-dots can be used in cellular imaging and multimodal bioimaging of cells and tissues. The possibility of using C-dots as fluorescent labels for cellular imaging was first demonstrated by Sun *et al.* who used PEG1500N passivated C-dots to non-specifically stain Caco-2 cells⁸⁶. Since then, non-specific intracellular imaging of uptaken C-dots in other cell types have been shown, MCF-7 fibroblast cells⁸⁷ etc. The confocal micrograph showed brightly yellow emission in MCF-7 cells. It has also been found that the emission mainly locate at cytoplasm region, suggesting the C-dots can pass through cell membranes and enter into cells²⁵.

N,S co-doped C-dots were applied for biological applications, they were directly applied in the imaging of peritoneal macrophages of mice without any further functionalization which represents that C-dots had penetrated into the peritoneal macrophages of mice. Furthermore, the photoluminescence intensity of the labelled macrophages showed no obvious reduction after continuous excitation for 20 min, suggesting that N,S co-doped C-dots possessed a remarkable photostability and low photobleaching and thus revealing the promising application of N,S co-doped C-dots in cell labelling⁸⁸.

Photocatalysis and photovoltaics :

C-dots can also serve as a catalyst in many reactions of biological and environmental importance. It is well known that C-dots have a broad range of absorption spectrum ranging spectral region from ultraviolet (UV) to NIR radiation, which enables C-dots to efficiently utilize the full spectrum of sunlight⁸⁹. Since the size of C-dots is very low it has very large surface volume ratio which is beneficial for absorbing more light and providing surface coordination sites in photocatalytic process. It result in augmented catalytic activity of C-dots based carbocatalysts^{90,91}. Photoactive C-dots are both excellent electron donors and excellent electron acceptors as revealed by a recent study and electron transfer with C-dots can be induced by photoexcitation. A recent study shows that vegetable-extracted carbon dots can enhance photocatalytic production of hydrogen⁹² and biomass chitosan based C-dots sensitizers for solid-state nanostructured solar cells⁹³.

Drug delivery :

C-dots due to its biocompatibility, excellent solubility and low toxicity is effective drug carrier for therapeutic payloads. But there are only few reports on C-dots as an efficient drug carrier. Due to high interstitial fluid pressure entry of most drugs is very daunting task. One of the finest solutions to avoid this situation is to synthesize smallest possible nanoparticles which are able to carry large amount of drugs and unload it to solid tumors. Hence C-dots can serve as a better targeted drug release carrier. Recently, Mewada *et al.*⁶³ have synthesized C-dots by microwave assisted heating of sorbitol using folic acid as navigational molecule (fC-dot) due to its widespread association with most of tumor cells. Before the exploitation of synthesized C-dots for targeted delivery of doxorubicin (DOX) to cancer cells, surface of C-dots was protected with bovine serum albumin (BSA) and thereafter DOX was grafted on it (fC-dot-DOX). At pH 5.8, there was dramatic change in the percentage DOX release after 4 h till 70 h where ~14% drug was found to be released. The therapeutic use of C-dots is very promising for future applications.

Conclusion

Herein, we have elucidated applications of C-dots in biological science, photocatalysis, sensing etc. C-dots have been proved tremendous advancement in field of medical science because of its bestowed excellent properties. Despite many proven advantages, the unique properties of C-dots are yet to be exploited. The PL mechanism of C-dots is debatable due to change in synthetic routes, surface functional groups and wide range of size distribution. Hence control over size is another problem which should be resolved to thoroughly understand its PL mechanism and expand its applicability in many other fields. Barring some C-dots most of C-dots have absorption band in long wavelength region (green and blue) which is unsuitable for *in vivo* imaging, therefore synthesis of C-dots emitting light in longer wavelength is desirable. The quantum yield of most of C-dots is very low as compared to semiconductor QDs is another major concern in practical applicability of C-dots. There are only few reports on C-dots exploitation in MRI scan, more study should be carry out in these fields. Therefore, widen its potential application in other fields besides drug delivery, anticancer agent, antioxidant, bioimaging etc. will bring the revolution in industrial fields.

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